

MODELLING AND CONTROL OF MECHATRONIC AND ROBOTIC SYSTEMS

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Annotation: The fields of mechatronics, robotics and automation are becoming one of the most important and relevant fields today. It is in these areas that the modeling of mechatronic systems and robot systems is one of the leading directions of industrial production and scientific fields today. In this article, the issues of modeling mechatronic systems and robot systems and their application in automation systems are considered and a conclusion is given.

Key words: Mechatronics, robotic systems, kinematic module, simulate, PID controller

Annotatsiya: Mexatronika, robototexnika va avtomatika sohalari bugungi kunda eng muhim va dolzarb bolgan sohalardan biriga aylanib bormoqda. Aynan ushbu sohalarda mexatron tizimlar va robot sistemalarini modellashtirish hozirgi kundagi sanoat ishlab chiqarish va ilmiy sohalarni eng oldi yo'nalishlaridandir. Ushbu maqolada mexatron tizimlar va robot sistemalarini modellashtirish va ularni avtomatlashtirish tizimlarida qo'llash masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan va xulosa berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Mexatronika, robot tizimlar, kinematic modul, simulatsiyalash, PID rostlagichlari

Аннотация: Области мехатроники, робототехники и автоматизации становятся сегодня одними из самых важных и актуальных. Именно в этих областях моделирование мехатронных систем и робототехнических

комплексов является сегодня одним из ведущих направлений промышленного производства и научных направлений. В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы моделирования макетных систем и робототехнических комплексов и их применения в системах автоматизации и дано заключение.

Ключевые слова: мехатроника, робототехнические комплексы, кинематический модуль, имитационное моделирование, ПИД-регуляторы.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the modelling and control of mechatronic and robotic systems is an open and challenging field of investigation in both industry and academia. The mathematical modelling of a mechanical system is indeed fundamental for the development of experimental prototypes. In particular, the kinematic model of a mechatronic or robotic system is essential for the proper definition of the path and motion law that the system has to follow during its operation. On the other hand, dynamic models are required to predict both the forces and torques acting on the system and those required by the actuators. These are ultimately useful to simulate scenarios and working conditions of interest. Furthermore, the dynamic modelling of a mechatronic or robotic system allows us to evaluate its time-dependent evolution and response under different input conditions. Indeed, a proper model can be implemented to improve the design and performance with different objectives, for instance, energy efficiency, and vibration reduction. Furthermore, the modelling of a robotic system is essential in path and trajectory planning to enhance control capabilities [5], and to increase kinematic and dynamic performance. Within this framework, proper control of an automatic system is essential for successfully completing a predefined task. This is especially the case when external disturbances are present, or when dealing with flexible systems in which mechanical vibrations have to be considered.

Modelling and Control of Mechatronic and Robotic Systems

This Thesis encompasses the kinematic and dynamic modelling, analysis, design, and control of mechatronic and robotic systems, with the scope of improving their performance, as well as simulating and testing novel devices and control architectures. A broad range of disciplines are included, such as robotic manipulation, mobile systems, cable-driven robots, wearable and rehabilitation devices, variable stiffness safety-oriented mechanisms, optimization of robot performance, and energy-saving systems.

Several papers deal with control problems, applied to both robotic systems and mechanical vibrations. In the full statement a novel sliding mode control algorithm is presented and applied for the trajectory tracking on a robotic manipulator with 3 degrees of freedom (DOF). The proposed controller runs without a precise dynamic model in the presence of uncertainties and enhances the response, fast convergence time, and accuracy of the tracking position.

The main goal of thesis is the design, simulation, and experimental verification of an adaptive feed-forward motion control for a hydraulic differential cylinder. The proposed solution is implemented on a hydraulic loader crane. Experimental results show the advantage of the proposed controller in reducing the cylinder position error and the adaptation to model uncertainties.

These present the modelling and control of a cable-suspended sling-like parallel robot for throwing a mass at a suitable time. The mass is carried at the end-effector by a gripper, which releases the mass so that it can reach a given target point. Mathematical models, which also account for the effect of cable elasticity, provide guidelines for planning the trajectory.

In the next, a 8-DOF integrated model of a semi-active seat suspension with a human model over a quarter is presented. A fuzzy logic-based self-tuning PID controller allows to regulate the controlled force on the basis of sprung mass velocity error and its derivative as input. Simulation results show that the semi-active seat suspension improves the ride comfort significantly by reducing the head acceleration

compared to passive seat suspensions. Moreover, it investigates the control of the over-critical vibration of a transmission shaft system with a device named Smart Spring, an active vibration control mechanism based on piezoelectric material. Simulation results based on a model implemented in ADAMS and MATLAB show the feasibility of the approach in reducing the vibration of the shaft system.

The next, I deal respectively with trajectory optimization and with a novel kinematic directional index for industrial manipulators. In particular, a “whiplashing” method is proposed to optimize the trajectory in order to increase the velocity of individual robot parts, thereby minimizing motion cycle times and exploiting the torque of the joints more effectively. The efficiency of the method is confirmed by simulation results on a 5-DOF RV-2AJ manipulator. A novel method is proposed for evaluating the maximum speed that a serial robot can reach with respect to both the position of the robot and its direction of motion. This approach, called Kinematic Directional Index, is experimentally applied to a SCARA robot and to an articulated robot with 6-DOF to outline their performances.

The previous presentation presents an energy-saving system based on a prefill system and a buffer system to improve the energy efficiency and the processing performance of hydraulic presses. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed system could reduce the installed power and pressure shock, increase energy efficiency, and provide the same processing characteristics as the traditional hydraulic press.

Several papers in this Special Issue are focused on the design, modelling, and control of mobile robots and systems. A hierarchical driving force distribution and control strategy for a six-wheel unmanned ground vehicle with independent drive motors is presented to improve vehicle maneuverability and stability. Authors investigate the effects of wheel slip compensation in the trajectory planning for mobile tractor-trailer robot applications. Experimental results on the prototype Epi.q

show that with the proposed approach it is possible to kinematically compensate trajectories that otherwise would be subject to large lateral slip.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that modeling of mechatronic systems and robotic systems is one of the most important areas. it is especially important in industrial production and academia. this article examines current problems in the systems and provides necessary advice for them.

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